

THE ANALYSIS OF CHARACTERS' STRUGGLE TO SURVIVE IN MARGARET ATWOOD'S WORKS

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Abstract

The article gives detailed description of characters' attempts to survive and find their real self in the society where they are victims, regarding to Margaret Atwood's novels. To identify self – related features was a long – term process in Canada due to being under suppression for many years. Being under the influence of the United States and Britain literary trends has made it difficult for Canadian writers to make their own way and to gain own values in the world literature. Margaret Atwood was one of the writers trying to describe a real Canadian identity in her novels. Being sacrificed and surviving were the parallel issues explored in Margaret Atwood's literary works and poems. The theme of survival has never lost its relevance in all time of existence of Canadian culture. This reflects both the struggle of the Canadian people with the harsh climate, outsiders and other threats, as well as the struggle of Canadian literature for recognition. Atwood described different aspects of Canadian literature representing sacrifice, failure and determination to survive

Keywords: self – identity, survival, victim, post- colonial country, struggle to survive, patriarchal society

Margaret Atwood, the author of one of the best-seller “The Handmaid's Tale”, is one of the most widely read literary figures in Canadian literature and a winner of many world famous prizes and awards. Among them are the Booker Prize, the Canadian Governor General's Prize, the Arthur C. Clarke Prize, the Franz Kafka Prize, and others. Margaret Atwood is a world-renowned writer, poet, critic and cultural activist. So far, Atwood is the author of plenty of books, including novels, short stories, poems, works of literary criticism and social history, and children's works. The most popular work by M. Atwood to this day is “The Handmaid's Tale” which was published in 1985, and its sequel “The Testament” published in 2019. Margaret Atwood is also well – known for her fantastic trilogy “MaddAddam” which includes a novel “Oryx and Crake” published in 2003, and followed by “The Year of Flood” in 2009 and the last one was “MaddAddam” published in 2013. All these books can be classified as philosophical or conceptual fiction (speculative fiction). However, most of M. Atwood's books are written in the spirit of realism and is dedicated to the description of typical Canadians. Margaret Atwood considered literature a mirror reflecting one's self and inner world. “*Literature is not only a Mirror, it is also a map, a geography of the mind*” [1,250] Great number of critics have noteworthy opinions about Margaret Atwood. “*Margaret Atwood “The Prophet of Dystopia” – her fiction has imagined societies riddled with misogyny, oppression and environmental havoc. These visions now feel all too real*” [4]

Margaret Atwood has tried to describe various themes in her novels referring to the past, present and future of Canada. One of them - the theme of survival - does not lose its relevance in all time of existence of Canadian culture. Canadian literature is a relatively young phenomenon; however, it has not been fully - isolated from British and American literature. The fact is that Margaret Atwood and the authors of her generation began to create Canadian literature and to write the first novels of Canadian literature out of emptiness. In

the first half of the 20th century, Canadian literature, which was not taught in any school or university in Canada, officially did not exist. However, Canadian youth studied English and American authors who were considered more significant than local native writers. Canadian authors, of course, existed and were even published, but they worked outside the tradition and attention of critics, the press and ordinary readers. A similar attitude of Canadians towards a Canadian writer M. Atwood explains the specific colonial thought inherited in many countries that have spent a long time under the influence of another more powerful state.

The protagonist of Canadian literature is the Survivor. According to M. Atwood, most Canadian writers look at the world through the eyes of a victim, constantly fighting for his existence. This reflects both the struggle of the Canadian people with the harsh climate, outsiders and other threats, as well as the struggle of Canadian literature for recognition. Survival is not only about the ongoing events, but also past and upcoming events which have clearly illustrated in Margaret Atwood's works. Margaret Atwood says: “*Every country or culture has a unifying or informing symbol at its core... Possibly the symbol for America is The Frontier...it holds out a hope, never fulfilled but always promised, of Utopia, the perfect human society...The central symbol for Canada...is undoubtedly Survival*” [2, 31]

The theme of survival is not about only Canada of today, but also of its past. To acknowledge one's own identity in the 20th and 21st centuries must be proven that the prerequisites for its emergence arose from the very formation of the state. This is dedicated to one of her best and most complex novels in terms of structure and composition “Alias Grace”, released in 1996. The book tells about the story of Grace Marks (1828–1873), a real girl who was accused of a double murder. M. Atwood, having done a lot of work with documents and eyewitness accounts, trying to reconstruct the events of those days. Grace Marks and her impoverished family - immigrants from Ireland moved to Canada in search

of a better life. However, here too, the same poverty awaited them. Hard work, unfair treatment of employers, hunger and cold deprive the heroine to commit a crime. In the fate of Grace Marks, the writer is looking for a reflection of the fate of young Canada with its poverty, social injustice, constant social conflicts and contradictions. And, perhaps more importantly, in the case of Grace Marks, the author traces the process of becoming a Canadian. Therefore, Grace Marks, stepping on the coast of Canada as an Irishwoman, after all the ups and downs and trials comes back to life as a Canadian after leaving prisons.

The writer's greatest contribution to survival as a Canadian and the search for their true "identity" was published in 1972 called "Survival: A Thematic Guide to Canadian Literature". This work was written in the 70s of the 20th century - as the embodiment of a new era in Canadian literature - a period of increased interest in Canadian literature and culture. This is a book describing Canadian's struggle to find a base in a national identity which can compete with the United States and Great Britain. To Atwood, the central image of Canadian literature is the theme of survival and its main character is the victim. Margaret Atwood claims: "*The central image of the victim is not static; four "Victim Positions" are possible (and visible in Canadian literature). These positions are:*

Position One: To deny the fact that you are a victim. This is a position in which members of the "victim-group" will deny their identity as victims, accusing those members of the group who are less fortunate of being responsible for their own victimhood;

Position Two: To acknowledge the fact that you are a victim (but attribute it to a powerful force beyond human control such as fate, history, God, or biology. In this position, victims are likely to resign themselves to their fate;

Position Three: To acknowledge the fact that you are a victim but to refuse to accept the assumption that the role is inevitable. This is a dynamic position in which the victim differentiates between the role of victim and the experience of victim.

Position Four: To be a creative non-victim. A position for "ex-victims" when creativity of all kinds is fully possible". [1,36-39]

Always being weak to struggle to the suppression of the USA, Canada is also included to one of the category of being sacrificed which is discussed in "Survival". Atwood described different aspects of Canadian literature representing sacrifice, failure and determination to survive. Atwood's concern for her nation is evident in this work, as she sought to develop various aspects of Canadian literature that represent victimhood, and survival. In fact, victimhood and survival are parallel themes that Atwood explores in her literary criticism and poetry.

In "Nature the Monster", the second part of "Survival", Margaret notes the importance of nature in Canadian identity and Canadian literature. In the literature of the Romantic period, nature is depicted as magnificent, fascinating, but after this period, it is a more complex and difficult entity. "*The Nature is giant, if a person objects it by fighting instead of accepting it and*

living in harmony, they will make it angry" [1,66]. According to Atwood, nature is a means of survival, under the influence of nature, a person must fight internally with his character and give external responses to nature. The writer says: "*Anxiety for one's survival is due to obstacles in the way. According to earlier writers, these obstacles are external - soil, climate and other forces, while according to the next generation of writers, the obstacles are both difficult to define and internal. These are the means of inner spiritual survival, not physical"* [1, 33]. Therefore, a person's encounter with nature is not only with external forces, but also with his own nature and self. Growing up in Canada's scenic bush country has a positive influence on Atwood's interpretation of a man and nature relationship. Atwood's views on nature are controversial, but accepted, nature connects men with their inner world and helps them discover their inner real identity. Thus, according to Atwood, living in Canada means being divided between the known and unknown because unlike the United States, Canada has a poorly developed sense of national identity. On the one hand, this is due to the fact that its territory is large and separate, and on the other hand, it is related to its economic and social relations with the United States.

Description of global problems today, such as consumer society, environmental pollution and people's struggle to find themselves in this society is another way of illustration of survival in Margaret Atwood's novels. For example, in the very first novel, "The Edible Woman", Margaret Atwood depicts the process of survival in a consumer society. The main character Marian gets mental illness. She is afraid of eating and gradually loses her physical health. Thus the girl refuses to consume because she herself is afraid of being consumed. In a consumer society, people will eventually begin to consume themselves - this is the main message of the book.

In her another novel "Surfacing", the nameless heroine also struggles with mental disease. The unnamed heroine of the novel is a typical Canadian woman with a Canadian way of thinking, passive, lacking her own identity, suffering from being a victim of society [3,94-95]. She becomes a witness to the plunder, destruction poached forests and lakes, on the banks of which she spent her childhood. The destruction of nature - the cradle of man - leads the heroine to madness. At the end of the novel, the fact that the hero has "one foot in the water and the other on land" on the deck means the ending is uncertain. However, uncertainty is an expression of the lack of society to talk about the success of the main character who faced and solved the problem she intended to. She managed to survive being the victim of the patriarchal society. Of course, she is her own hero by revealing and restoring her inner "self".

Not only were the past and present of Canada portrayed in Margaret Atwood's works, but the future existence of Canada is also imagined in her dystopian novels. It is noteworthy that in all the fantastic works of the writer, Canada is depicted as a silent island in the midst of total chaos. Citizens flee to Canada from the cruelties of the regime of the new state of Gilead, built,

by the way, on the territory United States ("The Handmaid's Tale"). In Canada, the heroes of the trilogy are looking for survival in "MaddAddam". Only in Canada, they can hide from the giant corporations, also originally from the United States. It is noteworthy that while Canada's mighty neighbor turns to a totalitarian state or to a hotbed of criminal gangs and the homeland of mad scientists in the future, Canada will never change its identity. The Canada of the future is virtually indistinguishable from the Canada of the present. For example, in "The Handmaid's Tale", while the former US is fighting a demographic crisis by disenfranchising its residents, Canada is doing a great job without sacrificing anything. Apparently with this, Margaret Atwood seeks to show that future Canada, taught long and bitter experience of survival, will be able to better cope with every problem. "Attention to the theme of oppression ... and the theme of 'survival' and 'sacrifice' is characteristic of many Canadian writers and due to relations between Canada and the United States, in which the United States dominated both politics and culture" [5,53].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the analysis of the theme of "survival" in Canadian literature based on the works of Margaret Atwood shows that the past history of Canada as a country has caused contradictions in the internal identities of its citizens. The characters' struggle to understand their place in life and their

identity suggests that it is the struggle of a real Canadian portrayed literally.

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